

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Acceptance note for **TEBT-2024-0012**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Present and future of AI, open science, and transparency in regulatory science
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0012
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley
Number of Reviewers	2 (two editors)
Submission Type	Meeting Report ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12741357
Evaluation Type	Editorial Review ▾ :: Round 2 ▾
Evaluation Date	23 Aug 2024
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Summary of article and editor recommendations

This article describes the take-homes from three presentations, breakout sessions, and a panel discussion from a pre-meeting workshop at the 13th Global Summit on Regulatory Science (2023). The main value in the article is providing a broad summary of contemporary concerns and a menu of discussion points in relation to the use of artificial intelligence in food and drug safety assessment. The authors responded satisfactorily to minor revisions recommendations from the editors, and the manuscript has therefore been accepted for publication.

Acceptance note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial review.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13365684>